

Phytochemical profiling of *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst for linking phenolics and flavonoid to antidepressant potential

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ABSTRACT

Dioscorea hispida Dennst. is a traditionally valued medicinal tuber recognized for its therapeutic relevance in neurological disorders. The present study sought to conduct preliminary phytochemical screening and quantify phenolic and flavonoid content in *D. hispida* to establish a biochemical basis for its potential antidepressant properties. Phenolic and flavonoid compounds are well-documented for their antioxidant, neuroprotective, and neuromodulatory activities, all of which play critical roles in the pathophysiology of depression. The findings revealed a substantial concentration of total phenols, including notable levels of ortho and bound phenolic compounds, alongside significant flavonoid content. This rich phytochemical profile highlights the potential of *D. hispida* to alleviate oxidative stress, regulate monoaminergic neurotransmission, and suppress neuroinflammatory pathways implicated in depressive disorders. These results provide a strong scientific rationale supporting the antidepressant potential of *D. hispida* and underscore the need for further in vivo and mechanistic investigations to validate its therapeutic efficacy

Keywords- *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst, Phenolic compounds, Flavonoids, Phytochemical analysis, Neuroprotective activity, Antidepressant potential

INTRODUCTION

Depression will be the second leading cause of morbidity increase after cardiovascular disease by 2020, which poses a major socioeconomic burden. Depression and related disorders account for approximately 60% of all deaths. Suicide is the most common situation of most depressive illnesses. Its symptoms include a sense of inadequacy, helplessness, hopelessness, guilt, or indecision, changes in eating and sleep patterns, a lack of energy and focus, a loss of interest and pleasure, agitation, a mental and motor slowness, and social withdrawal. (Santosh *et al.*, 2011). Medicinal plants have long served as an important source of therapeutic agents, contributing significantly to traditional healthcare systems as well as modern drug discovery. According to the World Health Organization (2023), a large proportion of the global population continues to rely on plant-based medicines for primary healthcare due to their accessibility, affordability, and cultural acceptance. In recent years, increasing interest in natural products has stimulated extensive

research on the phytochemical constituents of medicinal plants, as these secondary metabolites are responsible for diverse biological activities such as antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and anticancer effects. The bioactive compounds present in many herbal formulations have been shown to exert neuroprotective and psychotropic effects, suggesting their usefulness in addressing mental health challenges such as depression, anxiety, sleep irregularities, and cognitive impairments (Limanaqi et al., 2020).

The genus *Dioscorea* (Dioscoreaceae) includes over 600 species, mainly in tropical and subtropical regions. Many, known as yams, are valued as staple foods, nutraceuticals, and traditional medicines due to their diverse bioactive compounds such as alkaloids, saponins, flavonoids, tannins, phenolics, and steroidal saponins (Lebot, 2009; Price et al., 2017). It also contains important secondary metabolites with significant medicinal value. Steroidal saponins and alkaloids reported from these species show anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, and cytotoxic activities (Kumar et al., 2017).

Dioscorea hispida Dennst, or bitter yam, is a wild tuber native to South and Southeast Asia. In India, tribal communities consume it only after detoxification. Despite its raw toxicity, it has long been used in folk medicine to treat rheumatism, inflammation, skin diseases, and gastrointestinal disorders (Nair and Mohanan, 1998; Burkill, 2000). The toxicity of the tubers is mainly attributed to the presence of alkaloids such as dioscorine, which can cause neurological symptoms if consumed without proper processing. Tuber is laxative, toxic, and useful to heal the wounds. Decoction of tuber is an alternative, diuretic and used in chronic rheumatism, also as arrow-head poison. The roots are burned and the resulting smoke is utilized in magico-religious practices associated with spirit invocation and ritual awakening. (Bhogaonkar and Devarkar (2002).

However, *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst. remains poorly explored, particularly regarding detailed phytochemical profiling and the role of phenolic and flavonoid compounds in antidepressant activity. Therefore, the present study aims to evaluate the qualitative and quantitative phytochemical constituents of *Dioscorea hispida*, with special emphasis on linking phenolic and flavonoid content to antidepressant potential.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Fresh tubers of plant were collected from Chichati village Melghat areas in the mature growth stage with the help of traditional healers and identified and authenticate with the help of standard flora by Naik V. N (1998). Sharma et al., (1996)) Healthy and disease-free tubers were selected for the study.

Extraction of plant materials

The collecting plant materials were washed and shade dried. The dried plant material is powdered using mixer grinder, Preliminary phytochemical analysis was carried out using six solvents according to the polarity i.e. Petroleum ether, Benzene, Chloroform, Acetone, Ethanol and water respectively by Soxhlet method for 18 hr. Preliminary phytochemical screening done using standard procedures to identify constituents, as described by Trease and Evans (1979), Kokate (1988), Harborne (1998) and Sadashivan and Manickam (2005)

Content determination

For the Quantitative Phytochemical analysis Standard protocol for estimation of Total Phenolic Content (TPC), ortho-phenol and bound phenol described by (Thimmaiah., 1999.)

Total phenolic Content

The total phenolic contents (TPCs) of the extracts were determined spectrophotometrically with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent and calculated as mg GAE/g equivalents. For the preparation of the calibration curve, 1 mL of the gallic acid solution in ethanol. (at the concentration (100,200,300,400,500,600,700,800, 900,1000 µg/ ml) was mix thoroughly with 5 mL Folin- Ciocalteu reagent (diluted 1/10). After 5 minutes, 2 mL of the sodium carbonate solution (75 mg/mL) was added, and the mixture was allowed to stand for a minute. The absorbance was measured at 650 nm on a UV-Vis spectrophotometer. Then, a linear calibration curve (absorbance versus concentration) was developed. The plot was found to be linear across the ranged assay (100-1000 µg/ mL, $r^2 = 0.9809$). (Thimmaiah., 1999).

Ortho-dihydric phenols Content

The ortho-dihydric phenol content (ODPC) of the extracts was determined spectrophotometrically using Arnov's reagent method and expressed as mg GAE/g equivalents. For the preparation of the

calibration curve, 1 mL of gallic acid standard solution in ethanol ((at the concentration (100,200,300, 400,500,600,700,800 ,900,1000 µg/ mL)) was taken in separate test tubes. To each tube, 1 mL of 0.5 N hydrochloric acid was added, followed by 1 mL of Arnou's reagent (a mixture of sodium nitrite and sodium molybdate). After thorough mixing, 1 mL of 1 N sodium hydroxide was added, and the final volume was adjusted to 10 mL with distilled water. The absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. A linear calibration curve was prepared by plotting absorbance versus mg GAE/g concentration.

The ortho-dihydric phenol content of each extract was calculated and expressed as mg GAE/g equivalents per mg of extract.

Bound Phenolic content

The bound phenolic contents (BPCs) of the extracts were estimated using the Folin-Ciocalteu method and expressed as mg GAE/g equivalents. Bound phenols were released by alkaline hydrolysis of the extract residue with 2 M NaOH and incubated for 24 h at room temperature in the dark. The hydrolysate was acidified with concentrated HCl and extracted with ethyl acetate. The organic phase was evaporated to dryness, and the residue was re-dissolved in ethanol. An aliquot (1 mL) of the sample was mixed with 5 mL of Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1:10 diluted). After 5 min, 2 mL of sodium carbonate solution (75 mg/mL) was added, and the absorbance was recorded at 650 nm using a UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Gallic acid was used as the standard, and BPC was calculated from the calibration curve and expressed as µg gallic acid equivalents per mg of extract (Thimmaiah, 1999).

Total flavonoid content

The total flavonoid contents (TFCs) of the extracts were measured calorimetrically using AlCl₃ reagent and calculated as mg GAE/g equivalents. The gallic acid calibration curve was prepared by mixing 2.5 mL AlCl₃ reagent in ethanol (at the concentration 100,200,300,400,500,600,700,800,900,1000 µg/ mL with 2.5 mL AlCl₃. After 40 min the absorbance was measured at 415 nm on UV-Vis spectrophotometer and then a standard curve (absorbance/ Concentration) was developed. The plot was found to be linear across the range assay (100-1000 µg/ mL, r²>0.9853).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The plants have been utilized in traditional medicine for centuries to address various health conditions and are considered an essential source of pharmaceutical compounds. Several species within the *Dioscorea* genus are well-known for their extensive history of traditional medicinal applications (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Studies on the phytochemical composition of *Dioscorea* species have revealed important insights into the bioactive compounds found in its tubers, highlighting their potential therapeutic uses. Phytochemical analysis of species reveals the presence of saponins, tannins, flavonoids, sterols, polyphenols, glycosides and steroidal saponins. (Ghosh, 2015).

The preliminary phytochemical screening of *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst. was carried out using successive solvent extracts of increasing polarity, namely petroleum ether, benzene, chloroform, acetone, ethanol, and water. The results of qualitative analysis revealed the presence and absence of various phytochemical constituents, indicating a solvent-dependent extraction pattern. Alkaloids were variably detected across the extracts. Positive reactions were observed mainly in acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts depending on the reagent used, suggesting that alkaloids of different chemical nature are distributed across both non-polar and polar solvents. Carbohydrates and glycosides were predominantly present in acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts, as confirmed by Fehling's, Benedict's, and Molisch's tests. This indicates that these compounds are largely polar in nature and are efficiently extracted by polar solvents. Saponins showed positive foam test results in petroleum ether, chloroform, acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts, with the exception of benzene extract, suggesting a wide solubility range of saponins with a preference toward moderately polar to polar solvents. Phenolic compounds and tannins were prominently detected in chloroform, acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts, as evidenced by ferric chloride and lead acetate tests. The strong presence of these compounds in polar extracts highlights their hydrophilic nature and potential antioxidant properties. Flavonoids were observed mainly in chloroform, acetone, and ethanol extracts. This suggests that flavonoids in *D. hispida* are moderately polar compounds. Coumarins were detected in petroleum ether, ethanol, and aqueous extracts, indicating that these compounds may occur in both

non-polar and polar fractions of the plant Overall, the results demonstrate that acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts of *Dioscorea hispida* are rich in bioactive phytochemicals such as alkaloids,

carbohydrates, saponins, phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, and coumarins. These findings support the medicinal potential of the plant and provide a scientific basis for its traditional therapeutic uses.

Table 1. Preliminary Phytochemical screening of *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst.

Sr. No	Constituents	Chemical Tests	Extracts					
			P	B	C	A	E	W
1	Alkaloids	Hager's Reagent	-	-	-	+	+	+
		Mayer's Reagent	+	+	+	-	-	-
		Wagners reagent	+	-	-	+	+	+
2	Carbohydrates & Glycosides	Fehling's Reagent	-	+	-	+	+	+
		Benedict's Reagent	-	-	-	+	+	+
		Molisch's Reagent	-	-	-	+	+	+
3	Steroids	Salkowski Reagent	-	-	-	-	-	-
4	Saponin	Foam	+	-	+	+	+	+
5	Phenolics & Tannin	FeCl ₃ Sol	-	-	+	+	+	+
		Lead Acetate	-	+	+	+	+	+
6	Proteins	Biuret Reagent	-	-	-	-	-	-
7	Anthraquinone glycosides	Borntrager's Reagent	-	-	-	-	-	-
8	Cardiac glycosides	Keller-Killiani Reagent	-	-	-	-	-	-
9	Flavonoids	Lead Acetate	-	-	+	+	+	+
		Extract + NH ₃	-	-	+	+	-	-
10	Quinone	Extract +Conc. H ₂ SO ₄	-	-	-	-	-	-
11	Coumarins	Extract +10% NaOH	+	-	-	-	+	+

Note: P- Petroleum ether, B- Benzene, C-Chloroform, A- Acetone, E- Ethanol, W- Water

Table 2.-Phenolic and flavonoid content of *Dioscorea hispida* dennst. Tubers in different extracts

Sr. No	Phenolic Compounds	Weight of plant material	mg/gm of Gallic acid		
			Aqueous	Ethanol	Acetone
1	Total Phenol	1 gm	4.28	4.16	4.13
2	Ortho dihydric phenol	1 gm	0.58	0.53	0.82
3	Bound Phenol	1 gm	1.28	1.08	1.12
4	Flavonoid	1gm	0.48	0.58	0.54

The quantitative analysis of phenolic and flavonoid contents in tubers of *Dioscorea hispida* revealed the presence of considerable amounts of bioactive compounds in different solvent extracts. Among the extracts, the aqueous extract showed the highest total phenolic content (4.28 mg/gm gallic acid equivalent), followed closely by ethanol (4.16 mg/gm) and acetone (4.13 mg/gm). Ortho-dihydric phenols were found in maximum quantity in the acetone extract (0.82 mg/gm), whereas the aqueous and ethanol extracts showed 0.58 mg/gm and 0.53 mg/gm respectively. Bound phenolic content was highest in the aqueous extract (1.28 mg/gm), followed by acetone (1.12 mg/gm) and ethanol (1.08 mg/gm). Flavonoid content was comparatively higher in the ethanol extract (0.58 mg/gm), followed by acetone (0.54 mg/gm) and aqueous extract (0.48 mg/gm).

Phenolic compounds, particularly ortho-dihydric phenols and bound phenols, are known for their free radical scavenging activity and neuroprotective effects. Oxidative stress plays a significant role in the pathophysiology of depression therefore, extracts rich in phenolics and flavonoids may help reduce oxidative damage in neural tissues. Flavonoids are also reported to modulate neurotransmitters such as serotonin, dopamine, and norepinephrine, which are closely associated with antidepressant activity.

The antidepressant activity of the plant extract may be strongly correlated with its phenolic and flavonoid contents. Phenolic compounds, including ortho-dihydric and bound phenols, are known to exert antioxidant effects by scavenging reactive oxygen species, thereby reducing oxidative stress implicated in the pathophysiology of depression (Maes *et al.*, 2011; Rice-Evans *et al.*, 1997). Flavonoids, in particular, have been reported to influence monoaminergic neurotransmission by inhibiting monoamine oxidase (MAO) activity and enhancing serotonin, dopamine, and noradrenaline levels in the brain (Youdim and Bakhle, 2006; Mazzio and Soliman, 2012). Thus, the synergistic interaction between phenolic compounds and flavonoids may underlie the antidepressant-like effects of the plant extract.

CONCLUSION

The present investigation offers a detailed phytochemical assessment of *Dioscorea hispida* Dennst. tubers, thereby supporting its traditional

medicinal significance. Preliminary screening confirmed the presence of various bioactive compounds, including alkaloids, carbohydrates, saponins, phenolics, tannins, flavonoids, and coumarins, with notable abundance in acetone, ethanol, and aqueous extracts. Quantitative estimation revealed that the tubers contain a significantly high level of total phenolics along with considerable quantities of ortho-dihydric and bound phenolic compounds, indicating a strong antidepressant potential.

Overall, this comprehensive phytochemical characterization of *D. hispida* provides important insights into its bioactive composition and therapeutic potential. Establishing a clear association between phenolic and flavonoid constituents and their antidepressant activity may help substantiate its traditional applications and emphasize its promise as a natural source for developing plant-based neuroprotective and antidepressant agents. Moreover, the outcomes of this study may serve as a foundation for further pharmacological research, standardization, and effective utilization of *D. hispida* in medicinal and pharmaceutical fields.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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